

ORGANIZATION OF SPATIAL ORIENTATION AND VISUAL SUPPORT IN CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the difficulty children with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) have in understanding verbal instructions and social signals, the importance of spatial organization and visual support, various teaching methods that promote calmness and encourage independence, workplace organization, creating individual and group schedules, spatial zoning, the use of various teaching methods (visual aids, multisensory methods), and the development of independent learning and problem-solving skills.*

Keywords: *visual, UDL - Universal Design for Learning, zone, distribution table, academic skill.*

Introduction

Specialists often discuss the importance of spatial structuring. However, let's pause for a moment and consider: why is this so crucial? Children with autism spectrum disorders and other developmental characteristics, like most of their typically developing peers, use visual perception to reinforce the information they hear.

Verbal instructions and social cues are difficult to grasp, while visual aids allow for a better understanding of what is happening around them. Visual support created in the classroom is vital. It helps maintain calmness and encourages independence. According to research, people with autism spectrum disorder feel more comfortable in an orderly and predictable environment. To create such an environment, it is necessary to carefully select educational materials and devise storage places for them, which allows for maintaining calmness and encourages independence. It is essential to consider the organization of the workplace, the creation of individual and group schedules, zoning of space, and much more - that is, everything that surrounds the child in the educational institution.

Space organization and visual support

The main goal is to make the space predictable and understandable for everyone who is in the room and working with materials. In our projects, the adaptation of space, the presentation of educational material, and the organization of the educational process are carried out taking into account the main challenges of children with autism, the principles of applied behavior analysis, and the sensory characteristics of children with ASD. We also use systematic learning ideas and the TEACCH approach. This approach was developed at the University of North Carolina (TEACCH® Autism Program). In addition, we use the principles of UDL - Universal Design for Learning.

Here are some tips on how to organize space if there is a child with autism in the classroom.

Determine the number of zones in the class

The number and functions of different zones in the classroom depend on the size of the room, the number of students, and their needs in the educational and social interaction process.

Designing a classroom that meets students' needs helps:

- eliminate negative behavior;
- reduce anxiety;
- develop independence;
- increase the effectiveness of training.

Achieving success in solving these serious tasks is not easy. The first step on this path is to systematize the space that guides students' next actions. By moving from one work zone to another and following a modified schedule, a child with ASD (autism spectrum disorder) develops adaptability and learns to use skills in various conditions. For example, they first acquire skills individually with the teacher, then practice them in a small group, and finally apply them during a noisy break among many other children.

How are zones created in a classroom or group? The simplest way is to create visible boundaries of individual zones using furniture. Consider natural barriers: cabinets, screens, partitions, etc., so that students in adjacent zones are not distracted by other ongoing activities.

What kinds of zones can be created? Zones for group activities. Group activities may require different levels of adaptation depending on students' activity levels, communication abilities, and necessary support levels. Sometimes a simple classroom with desks arranged for frontal teaching is suitable. It will only be necessary to allocate spaces for frequently distracted students, those who don't know how to wait, and for assistants or tutors. However, such adaptation may not be sufficient, and the need arises to create areas for small group work, individual sessions, and independent work.

The arrangement of tables and workspaces relative to the blackboard should allow students to easily transition from working in small groups to whole-class activities and, if necessary, answering at the blackboard. Often, it's not possible to provide enough teachers in the classroom, so the teacher and assistants must monitor various simultaneous activities and move between small group workspaces and individual instruction areas. If you're in a similar situation, consider how to reduce movements across the classroom and organize different zones. Perhaps it's advisable to locate learning areas away from places where children might be distracted by sensory games, video games, or other engaging activities. There should also be tables for group work in the classroom, not just desks for individual work. This is important because children with autism spectrum disorders should have opportunities to play and engage with their peers.

A horseshoe-shaped table can be a good solution for organizing small group work. The teacher can see all the children, and the children can see each other's faces. The teacher is within arm's reach of each child and can quickly provide not only instructions and assignments but also materials and support. This is crucial, as maintaining a high pace of learning and social interaction is essential when working with autistic children. Usually, this is difficult to achieve if students are seated at separate desks with the teacher standing at the blackboard.

During breaks, you may need a small table to organize board games involving children of different levels, including typically developing peers. The teacher can see all the children, and the children can see each other's faces.

Classroom should have a zone for social activities and simple physical exercises: greetings and farewells, warm-ups during lessons, etc. This zone can be marked with a carpet or colored tape on the floor, where there is usually no furniture or unnecessary items. If chairs are needed,

they are brought in from other areas. Spaces for individual sessions can be organized differently depending on students' developmental levels, their sensory and behavioral characteristics, as well as the tasks they perform with teachers.

Area for individual study with a student. Moving from one room to another is a significant stress for many children with ASD. Additionally, transitions require time and create extra organizational challenges. Many children with autism and other developmental disabilities can only maintain attention for short periods. To increase the program's intensity and effectiveness, in some cases, zones for individual sessions with specialists and teachers can be set up directly in the classroom to reduce the number and duration of transitions.

In such places, tests can be conducted, pre-academic skills can be taught using discrete trial methods, initial communication skills can be developed, and regular preference assessments can be carried out; sometimes a token system is implemented here. In this area, a space should be allocated for the teacher to work one-on-one with the child. If a student needs physical assistance, it's necessary to prepare a place for an assistant or find a way for the teacher to work from the corner of the table so they can help the child sitting in front of them at any time.

Student's independent work area. For some children with ASD and other developmental characteristics, it's necessary to equip a special place with minimal distractions for independent work or working with a schedule. Here, a child receiving an incentive, for example, in the form of a tablet game, book, or Lego set, can effectively use their allocated time, while the teacher, continuing to work with other children in the class, doesn't lose sight of them and simultaneously monitors the time. Perhaps some students with significant behavioral issues also need a quiet corner where they can take a break from active classroom life. Try to furnish this place as safely as possible and in a way that isn't too interesting for the child, so they don't start using it for play or entertainment. Never use this area without pre-developing a behavioral plan in conjunction with school specialists; also, don't use it as punishment for inappropriate behavior. By sending a child who is misbehaving there, you risk reinforcing inappropriate behavior. For some children, such practice can be an incentive directed towards completing a more complex task, for others - a safe break within the framework of a preventive strategy that aligns with the developed behavioral plan.

If there is a child in the class trying to leave without permission, additional space adjustment may be required. Along with developing a behavioral plan and seeking alternative behaviors, it's necessary to organize the classroom space to prevent escape attempts. Such a child's workspace should not be near the door. The teacher, instructor, or assistant should be positioned between the door and the student. Also, workstations, student desks, and other classroom items can be arranged in a small maze-like formation between the student and the door.

Transition zones. Life consists not only of classroom activities but also of many movements, such as breaks, lunch, physical education or music lessons, going to neighboring classrooms, and so on. The importance of time intervals between these various activities is very significant for a child with ASD. Moreover, transitions usually take longer than we think. The life of a child with ASD can become much easier if we consider where they will be during transitions. If there are young, active children in the class, be sure to prepare waiting areas for them. It's possible to line up the children and expect them to remain silent, waiting for you to prepare the rest to move to another activity zone, but achieving the desired result will not be easy. However, sitting and waiting is much easier. Therefore, plan waiting areas near the door. If children need to line up to go to the cafeteria or another lesson together, allocate space for this and mark a clear

visual guide on the floor or wall in advance so they can understand who should stand where. Studies show that using visual channels in teaching people with ASD is most effective.

If a verbal alert doesn't work and is perceived as noise, use an item to be used in the next activity or an image of where the child will go. This helps them understand what will happen next and facilitates the transition from one activity to another.

Storage of manuals, toys, and other materials

For effective teaching in the classroom, textbooks, auxiliary materials, picture books and toys, laminated cards, and many other items are necessary. Often, children with autism spectrum disorders and other developmental peculiarities have a high level of distractibility, difficulties in distinguishing signals from noise, and problems with concentration. Therefore, never place all games and learning materials in an open space at the same time - this complicates students' social interactions and teachers' work. The more poorly organized the workspace, the harder it is to expect students to independently select the necessary materials for completing tasks, and the more difficult it is to expect classroom assistants to work quickly and effectively in developing academic skills or organizing games that match children's abilities.

For organizing materials, it is recommended to use containers, boxes, folders, etc., on which special markings can be placed. Use different colors to label and differentiate items that can be used by students, teachers, and assistants. Materials used by children should be placed in locations convenient for them. Markings on containers and folders should also be visible. Rarely used materials can be placed on upper shelves, while frequently used materials should always be within reach. If there are one or more students in the class who are constantly distracted by the computer, cover the monitor with a special case to indicate that it is not possible to use the computer at this time.

Visual aid

We all use visual aids to organize our lives, choose food in restaurants, understand directions, and for other purposes.

For people living with ASD, visual aid is one of the most essential tools. It's natural for adults to speak more when they think a child doesn't understand them. As a result, excessive information can overwhelm a person with ASD and make communication difficult. To improve comprehension, you need to speak less and use visual aids. The general rule for everyone who interacts with children with ASD is as follows: speak less and use visual assistance.

Conclusion. Visual support helps to focus and maintain attention. It provides information in a form that is understandable to children with special needs, clarifies verbal information, facilitates the understanding of abstract concepts such as time, sequence, cause-and-effect relationships, and also creates conditions for comprehending messages and eases transitions between activities or locations.

The main components of visual support are:

- visual organization: shows how the spatial environment and materials are limited, organized, or placed in certain locations (containers);
- visual clarity: drawing attention to important information (highlighting with colors, labels, underlining);
- visual instructions: shows where to start, the sequence of actions and steps.

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